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Characterization of vesicular trafficking and the secretory pathway in Alzheimer's Disease pluripotent stem cells: Syt/Stx family.

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We describe here identification of Syt15/15b, Syt17 and Stx7 as candidate therapeutic vulnerabilities made using study of total transcription in pluripotent stem cell models of Alzheimer's Disease.